

PROCEEDINGS BOOK

INTERNATIONAL MEDITERRANEAN CONGRESS

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

Edited by

Asst. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Emin KALGI

INTERNATIONAL
MEDITERRANEAN
CONGRESS

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

PROCEEDINGS BOOK

Edited by
Asst. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Emin KALGI

by
IKSAD GLOBAL PUBLISHING HOUSE

E-mail: info@iksad.com
izdasconference2@gmail.com www.izdas.org

All rights of this book belong to IKSAD GLOBAL Publishing House
Authors are responsible both ethically and juristically

IKSAD GLOBAL Publications – 2022©

Issued: 02.12.2022

ISBN:978-625-6380-19-6

CONGRESS ID

CONGRESS TITLE

INTERNATIONAL MEDITERRANEAN CONGRESS

DATE and PLACE

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

ORGANIZATION

IKSAD Institute

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Prof. Dr. Mykola VAS'KIV

Doç. Dr. Olha BYKOVA

Dr. Vedat AKMAN

Dr. Baurcan BOTAKARAYEV

Öğr. Gör. Cihan YETKİN

Elvan CAFAROV

Ali SÖYLEMEZ

NUMBER of ACCEPTED PAPERS

146

NUMBER of REJECTED PAPERS

35

PARTICIPANT COUNTRIES (21)

Türkiye, Morocco, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Nigeria, Iran, Vietnam, Azerbaijan, Lithuania, India, Indonesia, Algeria, Pakistan, Brazil, Portugal, Romania, South Africa, Spain, Ukraine, Malaysia, Taiwan

TOTAL NUMBER of INTERNATIONAL PAPERS

Türkiye (69), Other Countries (77)

EVALUATION PROCESS

All Applications Have Undergone A Double-Blind Peer Review Process

PRESENTATION

Oral Presentation

INTERNATIONAL
MEDITERRANEAN
CONGRESS

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

Proceedings Book

**MODELING AND DEVELOPMENT OF DIRECTIVE ANTENNAS WITH LINEAR
POLARIZATION FOR LABORATORY MEASUREMENTS**

**Emerson Gean Sousa Vieira^{*1,2}, Rennan Souza Ribeiro^{1,3}, Polyane Alves Santos^{1,4}, Kenedy Marconi
Geraldo dos Santos^{1,5}, and Tagleorge Marques Silveira^{6,7,8}**

^{*1}Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Bahia, Vitória da Conquista, Brazil.

²ORCID 0000-0002-7474-8551

³ORCID 0000-0002-1744-1633

⁴ORCID 0000-0002-4980-7011

⁵ORCID 0000-0003-4724-9252

⁶ UA- University of Aveiro, DETI, Aveiro, Portugal,

⁷ ISTECS – Instituto Superior de Tecnologias Avançadas, Porto, Portugal,

⁸ ORCID 0000-0002-6776-6057

Abstract

The period of hyperconnectivity, also known as the Internet of Things, is the connection of common objects with the internet, so new functions are inserted in people's routines, as the evolution of the internet of things has allowed to connect several common objects of the day to day of the people to the internet. The age of hyperconnectivity provides greater fluidity and mobility in networks. Thus, technological and more efficient hardware become necessary for a better connection in this period. Therefore, it needs the implementation of new equipment that can allow better access. Directive antennas are equipment that has the property of sending or receiving electromagnetic waves more efficiently in a certain desired direction, the polarization of the antenna defines the polarization of the waves radiated by it, when used in emission. The configuration and dimensions of the antenna also condition the way in which electromagnetic waves are captured by the antennas, when used in reception. therefore it becomes an important tool for telecommunication in the age of Internet of Things. Thus, this project aims to model and perform three-dimensional simulations, using CST Studio computational software, for the construction of planar dipole directive antennas in the frequency range 700 Mhz and 2.36 Ghz, thus serving to aid measurements in the laboratory. Furthermore, from the acquisition of simulated data, the results will be compared with the results of the works that served as a basis for this current project, so they will also be compared with the practical experiments carried out in the laboratory.

Keywords: Antennas, Directivity, Simulation.